

SAFETY DATA SHEET

Creation Date 16-Nov-2010

Revision Date 24-Dec-2021

Revision Number 5

1. Identification

Product Name Celite®

Cat No. : AC173460000; AC173460100; AC173460250

CAS No 61790-53-2

Synonyms Infusorial earth; Diatomaceous earth; Diatomite

Recommended Use Laboratory chemicals.

Uses advised against Food, drug, pesticide or biocidal product use.

Details of the supplier of the safety data sheet

Company

Fisher Scientific Company
One Reagent Lane
Fair Lawn, NJ 07410
Tel: (201) 796-7100

Acros Organics
One Reagent Lane
Fair Lawn, NJ 07410

Emergency Telephone Number For information **US** call: 001-800-ACROS-01 / **Europe** call: +32 14 57 52 11
Emergency Number **US**:001-201-796-7100 / **Europe**: +32 14 57 52 99
CHEMTREC Tel. No.**US**:001-800-424-9300 / **Europe**:001-703-527-3887

2. Hazard(s) identification

Classification

This chemical is considered hazardous by the 2012 OSHA Hazard Communication Standard (29 CFR 1910.1200)

Serious Eye Damage/Eye Irritation	Category 2
Specific target organ toxicity (single exposure)	Category 3
Target Organs - Respiratory system.	
Specific target organ toxicity - (repeated exposure)	Category 2
Target Organs - Respiratory system.	

Label Elements

Signal Word

Warning

Hazard Statements

Causes serious eye irritation

May cause respiratory irritation
 May cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure

Precautionary Statements

Prevention

Wash face, hands and any exposed skin thoroughly after handling
 Wear eye/face protection
 Do not breathe dust/fume/gas/mist/vapors/spray
 Use only outdoors or in a well-ventilated area

Response

Get medical attention/advice if you feel unwell

Inhalation

IF INHALED: Remove victim to fresh air and keep at rest in a position comfortable for breathing
 Call a POISON CENTER or doctor/physician if you feel unwell

Eyes

IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing
 If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention

Storage

Store in a well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed

Disposal

Dispose of contents/container to an approved waste disposal plant

Hazards not otherwise classified (HNOC)

None identified

3. Composition/Information on Ingredients

Component	CAS No	Weight %
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	100

4. First-aid measures

Eye Contact	Rinse immediately with plenty of water, also under the eyelids, for at least 15 minutes. Get medical attention.
Skin Contact	Wash off immediately with plenty of water for at least 15 minutes. Get medical attention.
Inhalation	Remove to fresh air. If not breathing, give artificial respiration. Get medical attention.
Ingestion	Do NOT induce vomiting. Get medical attention.
Most important symptoms and effects	No information available.
Notes to Physician	Treat symptomatically

5. Fire-fighting measures

Suitable Extinguishing Media	Use extinguishing measures that are appropriate to local circumstances and the surrounding environment.
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Unsuitable Extinguishing Media No information available

Flash Point Method - No information available
No information available

Autoignition Temperature No information available

Explosion Limits
Upper No data available
Lower No data available
Sensitivity to Mechanical Impact No information available
Sensitivity to Static Discharge No information available

Specific Hazards Arising from the Chemical
Non-combustible.

Hazardous Combustion Products
Silicon dioxide.

Protective Equipment and Precautions for Firefighters

As in any fire, wear self-contained breathing apparatus pressure-demand, MSHA/NIOSH (approved or equivalent) and full protective gear.

NFPA

Health 2	Flammability 0	Instability 0	Physical hazards N/A
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6. Accidental release measures

Personal Precautions Use personal protective equipment as required. Ensure adequate ventilation. Avoid dust formation. Avoid contact with eyes.

Environmental Precautions See Section 12 for additional Ecological Information.

Methods for Containment and Clean Up Avoid dust formation. Sweep up and shovel into suitable containers for disposal.

7. Handling and storage

Handling Wear personal protective equipment/face protection. Ensure adequate ventilation. Avoid contact with skin and eyes. Do not breathe dust. Do not ingest. If swallowed then seek immediate medical assistance.

Storage. Keep in a dry, cool and well-ventilated place. Keep container tightly closed. Incompatible Materials. Strong oxidizing agents. Strong acids.

8. Exposure controls / personal protection

Exposure Guidelines

Component	ACGIH TLV	OSHA PEL	NIOSH IDLH	Mexico OEL (TWA)
Diatomaceous earth		(Vacated) TWA: 6 mg/m ³		

Legend

OSHA - Occupational Safety and Health Administration

Engineering Measures Ensure adequate ventilation, especially in confined areas. Ensure that eyewash stations and safety showers are close to the workstation location.

Personal Protective Equipment

Eye/face Protection Wear appropriate protective eyeglasses or chemical safety goggles as described by

	OSHA's eye and face protection regulations in 29 CFR 1910.133 or European Standard EN166.
Skin and body protection	Wear appropriate protective gloves and clothing to prevent skin exposure.
Respiratory Protection	No protective equipment is needed under normal use conditions.
Hygiene Measures	Handle in accordance with good industrial hygiene and safety practice.

9. Physical and chemical properties

Physical State	Powder Solid
Appearance	Grey
Odor	Odorless
Odor Threshold	No information available
pH	5-8 10% aqueous solution
Melting Point/Range	1610 °C / 2930 °F
Boiling Point/Range	No information available
Flash Point	No information available
Evaporation Rate	Not applicable
Flammability (solid, gas)	No information available
Flammability or explosive limits	
Upper	No data available
Lower	No data available
Vapor Pressure	10 mmHg @ 1730 °C
Vapor Density	Not applicable
Specific Gravity	2.2
Solubility	No information available
Partition coefficient; n-octanol/water	No data available
Autoignition Temperature	No information available
Decomposition Temperature	No information available
Viscosity	Not applicable
Molecular Formula	O ₂ Si
Molecular Weight	60.08

10. Stability and reactivity

Reactive Hazard	None known, based on information available
Stability	Stable under normal conditions.
Conditions to Avoid	Incompatible products. Exposure to moisture. Avoid dust formation.
Incompatible Materials	Strong oxidizing agents, Strong acids
Hazardous Decomposition Products	Silicon dioxide
Hazardous Polymerization	Hazardous polymerization does not occur.
Hazardous Reactions	None under normal processing.

11. Toxicological information

Acute Toxicity

Product Information	No acute toxicity information is available for this product
Component Information	
Toxicologically Synergistic Products	No information available
<u>Delayed and immediate effects as well as chronic effects from short and long-term exposure</u>	

Irritation Irritating to eyes May cause irritation of respiratory tract

Sensitization No information available

Carcinogenicity The table below indicates whether each agency has listed any ingredient as a carcinogen.

Component	CAS No	IARC	NTP	ACGIH	OSHA	Mexico
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	Not listed				

Mutagenic Effects No information available

Reproductive Effects No information available.

Developmental Effects No information available.

Teratogenicity No information available.

STOT - single exposure Respiratory system

STOT - repeated exposure Respiratory system

Aspiration hazard No information available

Symptoms / effects,both acute and delayed No information available

Endocrine Disruptor Information No information available

Other Adverse Effects The toxicological properties have not been fully investigated.

12. Ecological information

Ecotoxicity

Do not empty into drains.

Persistence and Degradability Insoluble in water

Bioaccumulation/ Accumulation No information available.

Mobility Is not likely mobile in the environment due its low water solubility.

13. Disposal considerations

Waste Disposal Methods Chemical waste generators must determine whether a discarded chemical is classified as a hazardous waste. Chemical waste generators must also consult local, regional, and national hazardous waste regulations to ensure complete and accurate classification.

14. Transport information

DOT Not regulated

TDG Not regulated

IATA Not regulated

IMDG/IMO Not regulated

15. Regulatory information

United States of America Inventory

Component	CAS No	TSCA	TSCA Inventory notification - Active-Inactive	TSCA - EPA Regulatory Flags
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	X	ACTIVE	-

Legend:

TSCA US EPA (TSCA) - Toxic Substances Control Act, (40 CFR Part 710)

X - Listed
 ' - Not Listed

TSCA 12(b) - Notices of Export Not applicable

International Inventories

Canada (DSL/NDSL), Europe (EINECS/ELINCS/NLP), Philippines (PICCS), Japan (ENCS), Japan (ISHL), Australia (AICS), China (IECSC), Korea (KECL).

Component	CAS No	DSL	NDSL	EINECS	PICCS	ENCS	ISHL	AICS	IECSC	KECL
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	KE-21794

KECL - NIER number or KE number (<http://ncis.nier.go.kr/en/main.do>)

U.S. Federal Regulations

SARA 313 Not applicable

SARA 311/312 Hazard Categories See section 2 for more information

CWA (Clean Water Act) Not applicable

Clean Air Act Not applicable

OSHA - Occupational Safety and Health Administration Not applicable

CERCLA Not applicable

California Proposition 65 This product does not contain any Proposition 65 chemicals.

U.S. State Right-to-Know Regulations

Component	Massachusetts	New Jersey	Pennsylvania	Illinois	Rhode Island
Diatomaceous earth	-	X	-	X	X

U.S. Department of Transportation

Reportable Quantity (RQ): N
 DOT Marine Pollutant N
 DOT Severe Marine Pollutant N

U.S. Department of Homeland Security This product does not contain any DHS chemicals.

Other International Regulations

Mexico - Grade No information available

Authorisation/Restrictions according to EU REACH

Safety, health and environmental regulations/legislation specific for the substance or mixture

Component	CAS No	OECD HPV	Persistent Organic Pollutant	Ozone Depletion Potential	Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS)
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	Listed	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

Component	CAS No	Seveso III Directive (2012/18/EC) - Qualifying Quantities for Major Accident Notification	Seveso III Directive (2012/18/EC) - Qualifying Quantities for Safety Report Requirements	Rotterdam Convention (PIC)	Basel Convention (Hazardous Waste)
Diatomaceous earth	61790-53-2	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

16. Other information

Prepared By	Regulatory Affairs Thermo Fisher Scientific Email: EMSDS.RA@thermofisher.com
Creation Date	16-Nov-2010
Revision Date	24-Dec-2021
Print Date	24-Dec-2021
Revision Summary	This document has been updated to comply with the US OSHA HazCom 2012 Standard replacing the current legislation under 29 CFR 1910.1200 to align with the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labeling of Chemicals (GHS).

Disclaimer

The information provided in this Safety Data Sheet is correct to the best of our knowledge, information and belief at the date of its publication. The information given is designed only as a guidance for safe handling, use, processing, storage, transportation, disposal and release and is not to be considered a warranty or quality specification. The information relates only to the specific material designated and may not be valid for such material used in combination with any other materials or in any process, unless specified in the text

End of SDS